

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NAMUKOSE****FIRST NAME: MARY****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software (MSWord 2411 on Windows 11 Pro)

Key concepts

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Tips for writing a good essay (EUCLID 2024, 13-14)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 31-34)
4. Style guides (EUCLID 2024,40-42)
5. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24)

ESSENTIALS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

I am excited to present my first response paper as a Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) student in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (DSDD) at Euclid University. When I enrolled in this program, my first thoughts about the coursework went from sustainable development goals and countries' progress to diplomatic relations and how they influence development. Little did I know that first things first. Before I delve into the course's core topics, I must take preparatory courses that will guide me on this journey I have started. It's always easy to criticize other people's literature until you are told to write your paper based on your understanding of the text provided. My response paper is based on the insights gained after reviewing the course material for ACA-401D. The insights I gained include but are not limited to the steps in essay writing, tips for writing a good essay, plagiarism and its consequences, style guides, and the different versions of English.

2) STEPS IN ESSAY WRITING

Writing an essay is an exciting journey that requires a lot of preparation, support, and determination, but it's doable. According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024) essay writing is not a linear process, but it's essential to start early, define questions, and have an initial plan for the essay. The course material EUCLID (2024, 8) summarizes thirteen steps to be taken in writing an essay. I have taken note that it is essential to understand the key questions a writer wants to address, to establish points of view, and to research the topic from credible sources since other people might have done similar work on that topic; a writer needs to dedicate time to reading, understanding, and making notes. This forms a basis for creating an essay plan and organizing ideas. While putting ideas together, it is important to note that a good essay must have three parts: the introduction, the body, and the conclusion. It is always important to review your work after writing; this can help to identify more ideas, correct mistakes, and check for consistency. It is also essential to ask colleagues to read through your essay to ensure that references are well-documented before submission. Overall, I have learned that these steps will be necessary for writing my reference papers.

3) TIPS FOR WRITING A GOOD ESSAY

The course material provides valuable tips for writing good essays and writing good essays requires practice and time. Writers are readers, and readers are learners. Therefore, writing is a skill, and I must invest time and resources to improve this skill. The more papers I write during this course of the Ph.D. journey, the better my writing skills will be. Upon reviewing chapter one of the course pack, I found the following five tips necessary for writing a good essay, and I will keep them in mind throughout my academic writing journey (EUCLID 2024, 13).

- I. Clarity is key to the writer and the reader. Before writing, it is essential to think through the key topic of argument in the essay. It is important to stay focused and provide relevant arguments for the topic.
- II. Get the point right. Avoid making general statements in your essays. General statements depict a picture that the writer is unsure of what they are talking about and doesn't make good arguments.
- III. Keep it simple and sweet. One of the easiest ways to keep your essay simple is to avoid writing long sentences, using too many abbreviations, and not focusing on the words but instead on ideas.
- IV. Avoid plagiarism. Any writer needs to acknowledge other writers when they use their information by properly citing the sources. Plagiarism has serious consequences for any writer and is a serious offense.
- V. Writing should be fun. Readers get bored quickly with essays that lack creativity and style. It's essential to explore some styles in writing, avoid repeating words, keep your readers curious, and provide examples.

4) PLAGIARISM

According to EUCLID (2024, 33), plagiarism is “when a writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” This is wrong and unethical and has serious consequences. Chapter four of the course pack explains this concept in detail. It guides students in avoiding this serious academic offense by providing tips on making proper citations and quotations. It is important to note that in the case of common knowledge, citations may not apply.

5) STYLE GUIDES

A few years ago, I submitted my manuscript for review, and the reviewers returned with comments that followed a particular style. Little did I know that academic journals use style guides, and they expect writers who submit papers for review to follow the rules of the guides. After reviewing chapter five of the course materials, it was clear what style guides are, why a writer needs a style guide, and what style Euclid University recommends guides. I found the introduction to Chicago Rules insightful. It is important to note that there are certain concepts that I need to devote more time to understand but, most importantly, to practice. For example, the Chicago Manual Style needs practice as described in Chapter Six.

a) American Vs. British English

In this course period, it was revealing to learn about the different styles of English, their differences, and similarities. For most of my school life, I have mainly used British English. Still, it was fascinating to learn factors such as the population and size of the US

economy, its political position, the size and influence of its media industry, and the size of its publishing industry significantly impact the ‘world English’ (EUCLID 2024, 25). Since the American English style is recommended at Euclid University, I will be keen to use it more often moving forward.

6) **CONCLUSION**

As I embark on this learning journey, it has been a thrilling experience to pen down my first response paper based on the course material for the ACA-401D period (1) course pack and the orientation documents. There is a lot to learn and unlearn. The key concepts that have been emphasized will be critical in this Ph.D. program, and I will continuously learn and revisit the references and suggested reading material.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.